

Prediction and visualization of user emotion from music listening activity using ML

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Abstract— Music is one medium used by humans to communicate their emotions. It is extremely powerful and capable to induce and manipulate human emotions. In this paper, Music listening data mining and finding other musical features are significant for identifying a person's emotional state. This article focuses on identifying the mood of a user by analysing the songs he/she listens.

Keywords—music, mood, emotional states, machine learning, listening activity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Music at its core is another form of emotional communication which doesn't bounded by any languages. It has the ability to convey emotions to another person even without using words. This medium of emotional communication is now a days more popular with the invention of internet. Media streaming platforms like YouTube, Apple Music, Spotify, and so many others help music to be widely accessible and people are tending to listen to it more often. This leads people to relate their emotions with songs. Each one of them have at least one preferred song according to their mood.

That means, music is extremely powerful and it can manipulate and induce emotions in human beings. If we can understand the emotion conveyed in a song, it helps us to understand the emotional state of a person listening to it.

In this article I'm trying to figure out the emotions and mood changes of a person with the help of musical features and the listening activity. By analysing such data and properties of a song, we can clearly understand the emotion, mood, energy it creates in a user.

FEATURES

The results can be used for:

- Providing music recommendation based on emotional states of a user.
- Visual representation of emotional states of a person throughout the day, which helps them to understand their own mental states.
- Detecting depression at its early stages.

In order to detect the emotion in a music using Machine Learning we need some data. For collecting additional properties of a song, I'm using a Spotify API. For user listening history, I'm using an audio streaming service which is purely for educational purpose developed as a part of academic studies.

Machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence that analyses input data and train itself and thus enhances the purpose it is intended to perform using various learning strategies of algorithms. Machine learning is actually identifying the pattern from the given data set and use this information in decision making. It helps the humans to handle the huge volume of data to interpret, evaluate and make decision.

Here linear regression which is a machine learning algorithm is used for the analysis and it is a popular for supervised learning. As the name denotes it shows the linear relationship between and dependent variable (Y) and one or more independent variable (X).

That is,

Y= Dependent Variable (Target Variable)

X= Independent Variable (predictor Variable)

Here using machine learning and linear regression algorithm the sleep data is analysed. Analysis is based on factors that


```
data = pd.read_csv('hugelistingdata.csv', sep=',')
# Trim data
data = data[[
    "danceability",
    "energy",
    "loudness",
    "speechiness",
    "acousticness",
    "instrumentalness",
    "liveness",
    "valence",
    "tempo",
    "amazement",
    "solemnity",
    "tenderness",
    "nostalgia",
    "calmness",
    "power",
    "joyful_activation",
    "tension",
    "sadness",
    "mood"
]]
predict = "mood"
```

```
saved_model = open("mood.pickle", "rb")
linear = pickle.load(saved_model)
x_train, x_test, y_train, y_test = sklearn.model_selection.train_test_split(
    X, y, test_size=0.1) # Split data
predictions = linear.predict(x_test) # Gets a list of all predictions

for x in range(len(predictions)):
    print(predictions[x], y_test[x])
```

Output:

```
2.0000000000000005 2
2.0000000000000011 2
2.0000000000000005 2
2.0000000000000004 2
2.0000000000000018 2
2.0000000000000002 2
2.0000000000000007 2
2.0000000000000133 2
2.0000000000000044 2
2.0000000000000018 2
```

(Left side is the predictions and right side is the actual values)

Since the model is accurate enough to predict the mood rate of a new song, it can be added as new property for any song.

Data filtered is then split into two: depended variables and in-depended variables.

Then it is passed to the Linear Regression algorithm to train and the training process is looped for a certain time to obtain a model with highest accuracy and score.

Model with highest score is then stored as a pickle file for later usage.

```
x = np.array(data.drop([predict], 1))
y = np.array(data[predict])

best_accuracy = 0
for _ in range(2):
    x_train, x_test, y_train, y_test = sklearn.model_selection.train_test_split(
        X, y, test_size=0.1) # Split data
    linear = linear_model.LinearRegression()
    linear.fit(x_train, y_train)
    acc = linear.score(x_test, y_test) # acc stands for accuracy
    if(acc > best_accuracy):
        best_accuracy = acc
        with open("mood.pickle", "wb") as f:
            pickle.dump(linear, f)

print(best_accuracy)
```

The model obtained an accuracy of 1.0. This model can predict the mood rate of other songs based on the given training song data.

```
X = np.array(data.drop([predict], 1))
1.0
PS C:\WorkMachine\Seminar\algo>
```

The model with highest accuracy which have been previously saved as pickle file is then loaded for the prediction.

IV. VISUALIZATION OF USER EMOTION

Since we have the mood rate of each song which is predicted using the trained model, we can simply plot the listening time and mood rate of songs listened from the user listening history. This will create a diagrammatic visualization of user emotion throughout the day.

The same model can be used to visualize the mood or emotion a person like. If the user listens to songs with low mood rate, that represent his emotional state and liking.

The above figure shows the mood rate a person like based on the listening history. It clearly shows that he/she like songs with low mood rate, sine the listening duration of songs with high mood rate is low.

V. CONCLUSION

Now we understand the influence of music in human emotion and its benefits. Since the model is accurate enough to predict the emotional state, it has huge applications in many fields.

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